

METHODOLOGICAL SKILLS DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE FINANCIERS

Юлдашев Муроджон Комилжонович

Нукус инноватсион институты

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Резюме: Мақолада интерфаол таълим технологияларининг талабаларнинг ижодий фикрлашини ривожлантиришдаги аҳамияти ҳақида айтилган. Таълим технологиялари асосида ижодий фикрлашнинг психо-педагогик масалаларининг ечими белгиланган.

Калит сўзлар: интерфаол технологиялар, таълим жараёни, билим, шаклланиш, ижодий фаолият.

Резюме: В статье освещена роль интерактивных образовательных технологий в развитии творческого мышления студентов. Обозначены психолого-педагогические задачи, решаемые в процессе развития творческого мышления на основе образовательных технологий

Ключевые слова: интерактивные технологии, образовательный процесс, знание, формирование, творческая деятельность.

Summary: In article the of interactive educational technologies in developing of creative activity of students are considered. Pedagogical and psychological tasks, which should be solved in the process of creative thinking based on educational technology are denoted.

Key words: interactive technologies, educational process, knowledge, formation, creative activity.

By harmonizing the education system of our country with international education standards, ensuring the quality and competitiveness of personnel training in higher education institutions, increasing the quality level of the higher education system based on world practice, developing effective methods of implementing scientific and innovative achievements by widely applying the pedagogical design process to the continuous education system. are recognized as priorities. In the "Strategy of actions on the five priority areas of development of Uzbekistan", it is clear about strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions by carrying out works on construction, reconstruction, capital repair, providing them with modern educational and laboratory equipment, computer equipment and educational and methodological manuals. taking targeted measures is indicated as one of the priority tasks [1].

Providing educational material to future financiers is one of the main elements of a professor's activity. The following elements of the activities of future financiers belong to this stage of the educational process: perception, understanding and generalization of knowledge. But communicating the learning material to prospective financiers, connecting it with understanding and generalization is necessary for the professor-teacher to choose the right path for himself. he following scientific researches aimed at developing the competencies of future financiers based on a person-oriented approach are being conducted:

- teaching content and its teaching-methodical support;
- educational technologies;
- ensuring the objectivity of knowledge control;
- development of technologies for development of competent financiers based on a person-oriented approach based on the requirements of general world standards;
- conducting scientific research on the organization of independent education in lessons and extracurricular activities is gaining scientific and practical importance.

For future financiers, higher education is the most optimal period of self-improvement and development of quality, knowledge, skills and abilities that are professionally important for the successful implementation of pedagogical activities. In this process, future financiers include situations such as gathering, storing, transferring their knowledge, creating their logical structure, and learning ways to effectively use them in organizing their professional activities in the future. Today, future financiers are methodologically trained to:

- the need for forms of active education and social necessity are not fully satisfied;
- that they do not have sufficient professional and pedagogical training to organize educational activities aimed at professional formation;
- lack of necessary conditions for independent choice of content, method, and modern tools of education in professional formation;

- it is necessary to determine the ways and methods of eliminating imbalances, such as the insufficient formation of the required knowledge and skills, to draw the necessary scientific conclusions and develop scientific, practical and methodical recommendations by conducting scientific research and experimental tests based on them. Specializations taught in the direction of financiers also include practical tasks related to the creation of image and symbol concepts. They are like the development of creativity, the unity of logic and intuition, imagination and fantasy. These exercises are done in order to sharpen intellectuality. In the educational process, the goal is not only to activate imagination, but also to create a creative environment. Under these conditions, the cooperation of future financiers and professors-teachers will emerge. Joint positive action will certainly encourage a positive approach to the issue under study. Prospective financiers are tasked with creating an image using random tools, which may consist of a small text story and a graphic [2, 24]. From this point of view, each form of interactive work with prospective financiers allows for the use of specific technologies. Including:

1. Working together in pairs: "Work sitting face to face", "Work in pairs and together".
2. Work in small groups: "Aquarium" method.
3. Interactive games: "Role-playing games".
4. Discussion-based teaching technology: such as the "I choose my point of view" method [2.104]. Teachers are using a number of interactive methods in the course of the lesson. So far we have come across several types of teaching technologies. There are types of these technologies such as "Brainstorming", "Boomerang", "Fish Skeleton", "BBB" technology, "Insert table", "Lily flower", "Can you think", "Cluster". Of course, organizing lessons using such technologies will make it interesting and effective. If knowledge is individually understood, felt, learned through difficulties, then this knowledge will be fully and deeply assimilated. All of this depends on being responsible for the studied subject, learning skills, effective use of time in work planning, self-control, correcting mistakes, etc. Develops a constant mental activity on the part of future financiers and teaches them to use their time

wisely. With this, it will be possible to develop the independent educational activities of future financiers, to ensure the commonality of educational and scientific work, to attract future financiers to scientific and research work, and on the basis of this, it will be possible to improve the quality of training of mature specialists.

When practical training is organized in this way, students' ability to work individually and cooperatively increases. Each student comes to the training with independent preparation, as he feels responsible for the result of the work. The subject is fully mastered by the majority of students.

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